

ECONOMIC INTERDEPENDENCE OF BORDER COMMUNITIES AT ASSAM- BHUTAN BORDER: DYNAMICS AND OPPORTUNITIES

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Abstract: Borderlands function as dynamic arenas or spaces where the tangible everyday realities of the border people are played out, shaping human interactions and economic activities. The Assam-Bhutan border is one of the oldest in Indian history, dating back to Ahom rule in 1228 AD. Owing to spatial proximity and shared socio-cultural ties, the economic activities of the border people and their interdependency have naturally evolved, fostering mutual benefits for the people residing on both sides of the border. The border communities have long relied on each other to sustain their livelihoods. This paper is an attempt to explore the economic interdependency of the border people across the Assam-Bhutan border through primary and secondary data, semi-structured interviews, and open-ended discussions. It offers insights into the resilience of traditional trade networks in border regions and their potential to promote regional economic integration. The findings of the study show the importance of the border *haats*, the promotion of local economies, and flow of labour to Bhutan, exhibiting the interdependency of the border communities of Assam and Bhutan.

Keywords: Assam-Bhutan border, Border communities, Livelihood, Formal trade, Border *haats*, Labour flow

1. Defining the Border

The lines or boundaries that delineate geographical territories are referred to as “borders”. According to the International State-Centric System, borders are acknowledged as the dividing lines between countries and serve to define sovereign entities (Majaw, 2021). The concept of borderland pertains to the regions that serve as a transitional space between two distinct regions. These regions are characterized by a blend of cultural, social, political and economic traits from both sides of the border, fostering a dynamic space for interaction (Baud and Van Schendel, 1997; Prescott, 2014). One of the ‘paradoxes of borders’ is that borders embody varying circumstances and political dynamics between nations that simultaneously divide and unite people at the same time (Pinzon

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